

OVERCOMING PRAGMATIC PROBLEMS IN THE PROCESS OF SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6477217>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th April 2022

Accepted: 10th April 2022

Online: 15th April 2022

KEY WORDS

translation, pragmatic problem, linguistics, types of translation, simultaneous translation.

ABSTRACT

From this paper work I write what is the simultaneous translation and where can we use translation is an activity that consists in variative re-expression, re-coding of a text generated in one language into a text in another language, carried out by a translator who creatively chooses an option depending on the variable resources of the language, the type of translation, the tasks of translation, the type of text and under the influence of one's own personality; translation is also the result of this activity,

Translation in the study and improvement of foreign languages in Uzbekistan. It is no secret that in the conditions of modern globalization here is a growing demand for learning foreign languages. In particular, Decree of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov dated December 10, 2012 No. PP-1875 "On measures to further improvement of the system of studying foreign languages «important in this regard. These measures are aimed at creating young generation of modern thinking.

Among developed countries, our native language is also among the international languages in the hope of adding from other languages to our native language and vice versa translation from Uzbek directly into foreign language, that is, without any other language. The pace of development is growing rapidly. Especially the country has been working for a long time actively engaged in translation. However, lately years, a lot of interpreting, including

simultaneous translation, increased demand for time. Simultaneous translation studies and the use of simultaneous translation strategies in English and Uzbek are illustrated and illustrated relevance of the topic.

The article is devoted to investigation of the specifics of simultaneous interpretation as a top of the translation skills, which determines high demands to the level of development of translation competence. The subject of research is the study of modern approaches to the classification of errors that occur in the simultaneous interpreting activity.

In the process of implementing of the investigation method of analysis, systematization and generalization, linguistic methods of lexicasemantic, grammatical, discursive and contextual analysis were used. On the basis of the investigation it was found that in the most general form translative errors can be divided into semantic and language ones.

Each of the categories may be additionally divided into some subcategories. Semantic errors are distortions of the original pragmatics, deviations from the norm, providing disinforming impact on the recipient. Language errors do not affect the conceptual content of the original, affecting mainly on his perception by the audience of receiving cultural model. In the frames of the investigation errors from the practical simultaneous interpreting practice are given, which allows to demonstrate the functioning of different types of errors in the modern interpretation.

Preparation for the translation of the text aims analyze the text for the conditions of its creation, functional orientation, content and degree of complexity of the language. As a result, the translator selects appropriate dictionaries, reference books, similar texts in the target language, as well as other related literature, which will serve as a reference when creating the translation text. At the same stage, the translator is determined with the translation strategy, since he must highlight the primary and related translation tasks.

Results of the investigation, identification of mechanisms, possible reasons, which lead to mistaken interpretation in the process of simultaneous translation, may be successfully used in the optimization of process of translation in interpreters' practice, in the education of the interpreters, as materials in the development of theoretical and methodological literature in translation studies. The authors conclude that the interpretation is one of the most difficult types of translation, a complex, gradual psychological process that takes place under extreme conditions, leading to errors

in the speech of simultaneous interpreter. It is impossible to completely avoid erroneous interpretation and reconstruction of the original discourse; however, the understanding of the mechanisms of deviations from the norm, the use of appropriate translation strategies allows one to avoid semantic errors that distort the original pragmatics.

The translation process is usually divided into two stages. The first of these is the analysis of the original text in order to achieve its full understanding, extracting from it the full depth of meaning. The second stage of synthesis, i.e. vesting this meaning in a new foreign language form. In the process of translation, these two stages are closely related. The understanding of the original by the translator is a special understanding, different from the understanding of the same text by a person who perceives it without the intention of translating. Understanding the text in translation", i.e. oriented translation, there are two characteristic features:

- a) obligatory final conclusion about the content of the translated text and the most complete understanding of the source text;
- b) being conditioned by the structure of the target language or understanding foreign text through the prism of the features of the Russian language.

The first stage of translation activity, namely the perception of a foreign language text, is a complex sensory-thinking process, which is based on the simultaneous implementation of the analytical and synthetic functions of the brain and sensory organs. Comprehension is carried out with the help of the formation and formulation of thoughts, i.e. with the help of inner speech. The main question is, with the help of what language

means is comprehension carried out and how high is the degree of intensification of its flow. The highest degree presupposes the obligatory linguistic formulation of thought. As for linguistic means, comprehension can be carried out by means of the original language, or, with a high level of proficiency in this type of speech activity, in the target language, and with a high skill of the translator, using the means of an internal individual subject-schematic semantic code. Any speech work, in addition to the linguistic material from which it is built, requires as a necessary condition for its existence the presence of three more components: the topic of the message, the situation in which the communicative act is carried out and the participants in this act, who have both linguistic and extralinguistic knowledge.

Accounting for non-linguistic moments is one of the necessary conditions for achieving translation adequacy, since in many cases the content of the text is revealed through them. It is known that the volume of these non-linguistic factors is not the same for different peoples, so the translator should not hope that the object described, for example, in the source text (will be available to the representative of the translating language, in connection with which the translator should have all the necessary competencies to convey the content of in a form understandable for the translation receptor. In linguistic literature, this moment is called the pragmatic aspect of translation. "The concept of pragmatics in linguistics (and, more broadly, in semiotics) is by no means reduced to the concept of pragmatic meanings of linguistic (and in general sign) units.

The second stage of the translation process is the formation of the main meaning of the future message. In other words, at this stage there is a need to comprehend the relationship "meaning - idea", as well as recoding. If comprehension is carried out in the target language, then the formation of meaning is at the same time and the formation of ideas, and the process of comprehension includes the process of recoding. The recoding process in this case is not realized, since it is highly automated. At the third, final stage of translation activity, the expression of the statement is carried out, its reconstruction using the means of the target language,

In the most general form, the causes of errors can be divided into extralinguistic, associated with social conditions, and intralinguistic, associated with the internal resources of the language system. The main extralinguistic reason is the spontaneity of the speaker's speech, the influence of the social environment, the dependence of the speaker's speech on his social affiliation. This group may include deviations from the norm, due to inadequate use of a meaning that does not correspond to the communicative situation, the language register associated with the social situation.

Interlinguistic errors are due to the rhizomatic potential of the language system, the constant expansion of the connotative range of lexemes, the desire of the simultaneous interpreter to give expressiveness to the translated discourse. The reasons for the occurrence of linguistic errors include the desire for hypercorrection - "erroneous grammatical use associated with excessive implementation of the desired rule" [7]; implementation of speech behavior by

analogy with the norms of the native language.

Language errors, "expression errors" do not distort the conceptual content of the original, have a significant impact on the perception of the translated text. Based on the level of the language in which the error was made, in the most general form, the inaccuracies of the language representation

can be divided into lexical, morphological, syntactical, spelling and punctuation errors [10]. Within each specified category, it is possible to subdivide into subtypes, for example, within the framework of lexical errors, it is possible to single out a subtype of errors in management, tautology, and so on. "Errors of expression" are usually eliminated in the process of self-editing.

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